

Deliverable 1.3 – Data Management Plan

— Executive Summary —

The methodology that the PALOMERA project is designed upon is based on data collection and analysis around the political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental factors of Open Access (OA) book publishing. Data varies from policy and framework documents to survey and interview transcripts. The methodology adopts a stakeholder-centric approach that is capable of capturing dimensions which plays a key part in understanding and supporting the progress of OA book policy and practice. The data collection process is guided by the goal of fulfilling these key dimensions by addressing issues in all ERAs countries, by collecting complex data that cover all PESTLE factors, by considering all actors involved in OA book publishing at various stages of the research lifecycle.

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- Methodology
- Data collection
- Data management
- Policy
- PESTLE

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² <https://libraryjuiceacademy.com/instructor/beth-knazook/> (last accessed on 18 December 2024)

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Table of Acronyms

Acronyms	
ALLEA	European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities
AMU	Université D'Aix Marseille
BPCs	Book Processing Charges
CAQDAS	Computer Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis Software
CC 0	Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication
CC-BY	Creative Commons Attribution International Public License
CoNOSC	Council for National Open Science Coordination
CRAFT-OA	Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access
DACH	Deutschland (Germany), Austria, Confœderatio Helvetica (Switzerland)
DARIAH	The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DESCA	Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication
DoA	Description of Actions
EC	European Commission
ERA	European Research Area
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESF	European Science Foundation
EU	European Union
EUA	European University Association
FAIR	Findable. Accessible. Interoperable. Reusable.
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IBL PAN	Instytut Badań Literackich Polskiej Akademii Nauk
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
JISC	Joint Information Systems Committee
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIBER	Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche – Association of European Research Libraries
M#	Month
MWS	Max Weber Stiftung
NB	Nota bene
OA	Open Access
OABN	Open Access Book Network
OABT	OAPEN OA Books Toolkit

Acronyms	
O AeBU	Open Access eBook Usage Data Trust
O APEN	Open Access Publishing in European Networks
O ASPA	Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association
O ATP	Open Access Tracking Project
O BP	Open Book Publishers
O ER	Open Educational Resource
O PERAS	Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities
O S	Open Science
PEDR	Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (while in this document it will be referred to as Dissemination, Outreach, Engagement, and Exploitation Plan)
PALOMERA	Policy Alignment of Open Access Monographs in the European Research Area
PESTLE	Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal and Environmental factors
RFO	Research Funding Organizations
RPO	Research Performing Organizations
SPARC Europe	Scholarly Publishing and Academic Resources Coalition
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
UGOE	Georg August Universität Göttingen
UC	University of Coimbra
UNIBI	University of Bielefeld
WP#	Work Package
ZRC SAZU	The Research Center of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts

1 Introduction

The PALOMERA project collects, structures, analyzes, and validates knowledge about OA book policies across the ERA. To achieve that the major objective of the project relies on obtaining and coordinating qualitative and quantitative data on the OA book policy landscape in Europe, understanding the challenges preventing RFOs and RPOs from developing and aligning on policies for OA books and to helping them to develop policies and strategies that will advance the transition to OA books.

This document represents the current state of the DMP document and supersedes the previous document, *D1.3 Data Management Plan v1.6*, to which this is an update. Specific changes to the previous version are as follows:

- update on data collection and data types
- update on academic/research publications
- update on ethical aspects
- update on sustainability aspects and resources

A previous update was submitted internally to project partners at month 16 of the project (April 2024). The update was delivered after both a review of the existing DMP and the Grant Agreement, as well as consultation with all WP Leaders. As a result, no deviations from the initial version (1.6) were spotted and no issues in the project's data management practices were identified. This is due essentially to the great care that was dedicated to the initial DMP redaction, which tried to extensively capture data emerging within the project and define clear processes in how it should be managed.

2 Data collection and data types overview

2.1 Data collection and scope

A mixed method approach was adopted to gather both quantitative and qualitative data for further analysis. As a primary source of data, the project re-used existing data, from 2012 till 2022, like:

- policy documents,
- gray literature,
- research articles,
- reports,
- outputs of other projects,
- quantitative datasets from various sources (incl. bibliographic and market data) which could be aggregated for new analytical insights.

A major part of the data collection was created during the project itself by conducting the survey and a series of interviews with selected stakeholders that allowed for a more in-depth understanding of particular challenges and policies. The survey was collected anonymously, but data obtained during the interview was applied to GDPR restrictions of minimization and

pseudonymization. Information related to the data protection and ethics are described in section 6.1. Safeguards for personal data handling.

2.2 Overview of the data types within the project

Collected data consisted of all kinds of types and formats: .docs, .xlsx, .mp4, .jpeg, .pdf. Overview of the data types, location and access is provided in Table 1 on the following page.

Data type.	WP/ Task	Size, volume, format	Location	Data access
Project administration				
Project administration data, including personal data (textual, tabular) Subject to GDPR regulations, see the dedicated section below.	WP1	.PDF/A, .docx/.odt, .xlsx, Google docs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The project's Google Shared Drive 	Project Level Access Only
Event management data (including personal data, textual, tabular, recordings) Subject to GDPR regulations, see the dedicated section below.	WP1, WP5	.PDF, .docx/.odt, .xlsx, Google docs, .MP4 approx. 4GB each	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The project's Google Shared Drive 	Project Level Access Only
Platform usage data (user statistics of the project website, blog(s), social media platforms, webinar platforms) Subject to GDPR regulations, see the dedicated section below.	WP5	Platform dependent statistics, .xlsx	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Embedded in the respective platforms (Twitter, Zoom, Instagram, Youtube, LinkedIn, Hootsuite, Mastodon, project subpage on the OPERAS website), WP5 tracker 	Project Level Access Only
Instructional video recordings Subject to GDPR regulations, see the dedicated section below.	WP2, WP4	.MP4 (approx 400 MB each)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Zoom Cloud The project's Google Shared Drive 	Project Level Access Only

Dissemination				
Video recordings of public meetings, webinars Subject to GDPR regulations, see the dedicated section below.	WP5	.MP4 (approx 400 MB each)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zoom, • YouTube 	Open Access (CC-BY 4.0)
Content delivered via the websites (news items, event reports etc.)	WP5	.HTML plus related files: .css, .xslt, .js, .es	Subpage hosted by the OPERAS website, newsletter	Open Access (CC-BY 4.0)
Slides presented at public events	All WPs	.pptx, .PDF/A	The project's Google Shared Drive, PALOMERA Zenodo	Open Access (CC-BY 4.0)
Deliverable reports, recommendations (textual)	All WPs	.docx/.odt, .PDF/A	EC portal, PALOMERA Zenodo, DSpace as a Knowledge Base	Open Access (CC-BY 4.0)
Research papers resulting from the project	All WPs	.PDF/A, .TEI-XML, .EPUB, .JSON	Publisher's platform, PALOMERA Zenodo, DSpace as a Knowledge Base	Open Access (CC-BY 4.0)
Primary data sources				
Unstructured multilingual textual data (policy documents and other relevant textual sources and their contextualizing documents)	WP2	.PDF/A, .HTML, .JPG (snapshots), Google sheets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PALOMERA Zotero collection, • The project's Google Shared Drive • DSpace as Knowledge Base (selected records, see explained below) 	Open Access (CC-BY 4.0, CC0)
Data collection notes	WP2	.xlsx, Google sheets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The project's Google Shared Drive 	Open Access CC0

Bibliographic data from BASE and OpenBPC	WP2 -T2.1	.XML, .JSON	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The project's Google Shared Drive, • PALOMERA Zenodo, • DSpace as Knowledge Base 	Open Access CC0
Survey data	WP2 -T2.1	.XML	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The project's Google Shared Drive, • PALOMERA Zenodo, • DSpace as Knowledge Base 	Open Access (CC-BY 4.0)
Raw interview data - recordings and transcripts Subject to GDPR regulations, see the dedicated section below.	WP2 -T2.2 WP4 -T4.2	.docx/.odt, .PDF/A 300MB .MP3 100MB each, 5GB total	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recordings: Zoom Cloud • Transcripts: The project's Google Shared Drive 	Task Level Access Only
Stakeholder database internal survey and stakeholder database documents Subject to GDPR regulations, see the dedicated section below.	WP5	.xlsx /csv Google sheets 400 KB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The project's Google Shared Drive 	Project Level Access Only
Derived data/enrichments				
Interview data - anonymised transcripts and excerpts	WP2	.HTML .docx/.odt .PDF/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PALOMERA Zenodo, • DSpace as Knowledge Base 	Open Access (CC-BY 4.0)
Textual, tabular data, encoded by the Computer Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis Software	WP3	.CAQDASMa xQDA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PALOMERA Zenodo, • DSpace as Knowledge Base 	Open Access (CC-BY 4.0)
Vocabularies (standard or project-specific) used during the project	WP2, WP3	.XLSX/.CSV	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DSpace as Knowledge Base 	Open Access (CC-BY 4.0)

Table 1 Data types and format

2.3 Research data curation workflow

The strong horizontal cohesion of the project design significantly reduced risks and possible limitations of data curation. That said, within the project, there were few data curation workflows run in parallel and instead, the work was largely organized in terms of successive steps where the WP 2-4 built on data curation done in previous work packages. The illustration below sums up the major research data collection and curation processes (excluding administrative and project management data).

Figure 1 Research data curation workflow

To embrace the plurality of ownership but still reduce fragmentation of resources, digital resources from different national, institutional contexts were connected by the data landscape review and have been stored in the Zotero library (Zotero³ | Your personal research assistant). Zotero data collection served as a data storage for quantitative data during the project, accessible to all PALOMERA project partners.

Collected in WP2 material (starting at M2), which was a mix of quantitative and qualitative data, was selected for the analysis and was pre-coded with the use of Computer Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis Software to identify excerpts reflecting the central issues related to the main objectives of the project. Pre-coded documents were further analysed by WP3.

During the analysis phase (starting at M12), the collected materials were evaluated with respect to their suitability for inclusion as primary sources for the public Knowledge Base⁴ that was designed to display the collected data and analyses, and/or published as such openly as research data through a repository, or repositories specified in “3.2. Findable”.

³ <https://www.zotero.org/> (last accessed on 18 December 2024).

⁴ Knowledge Base permanent URI: <https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.14219/5>

The Knowledge Base consists of an open-source repository (PALOMERA Repository) developed and coordinated by OAPEN to store the data in a structured way. The Knowledge Base was integrated into an updated version of the OA Books Toolkit which serves as a public interface to give easy access to the data that is displayed.

The selection criteria for Open Access content and a multiple tier to access data is specified below under “3.3 Accessible”.

2.3.1 File naming conventions

File naming conventions for the data collection phase are specified in the Data Collection Methodology document and in the Interviewer Handbook ([Appendix 4](#)).

For administrative, project management and dissemination data, there was no strict naming policy in place. Work packages and within work packages, task leaders decided on the optimum level of granularity in this respect and made sure that creators, curators harmonized their files along a coherent, shared policy.

2.3.2 Versioning policy

Version control was implemented through the repositories used in the project (Zenodo and Dspace for the Knowledge Base). For documents created during the research process the versioning system is provided in a table below:

Version	Date	Change Editors names	Changes
1.0	YEAR/MM/DD	NAME SURNAME	
1.1	YEAR/MM/DD	NAME SURNAME	Minimal change
1.2	YEAR/MM/DD	NAME SURNAME	Minimal change
2.0	YEAR/MM/DD	NAME SURNAME	Substantial change

Table 2 Versioning policy

2.4 Roles and responsibilities

During the project WP Task Leaders were responsible for regular export of the data from their personal computers to the PALOMERA Google Shared Drive.

Regular export of ZOTERO library (together with the assembled full texts) was taken care of by IBL PAN and was deposited at the PALOMERA Google SharedDrive, as well as at the IBL PAN Google Drive for backup.

UGOE was responsible for quantitative data collection, e.g., including survey, national libraries queries, bibliometric data which were exported to PALOMERA Google SharedDrive.

Hanken, in cooperation with UGOE and IBL PAN, was responsible for data coding, enrichment and preparation for analysis. Hanken also mainly led the analysis process.

OAPEN as a data steward in the project put the effort in data curation through the selection of the materials (outputs) and the preparation of descriptive examples, case studies, and articles published in Knowledge Base and as part of the extended OABT.

Depositing project outputs to the PALOMERA Zenodo community was the responsibility of OPERAS.

3 FAIR data and Openness by design

This section describes the provisions made to accommodate the FAIR principles and thereby future usage of PALOMERA data resources.

3.1 OPEN by design

Besides intending to implement the European Union's Open Science policy⁵ through the PALOMERA proposal, consortium members implemented an open, transparent, and re-usable methodology during the project length.

OS practices have been included in each WP:

- WP1: the DMP was constructed to maximise the openness and reuse of the project outputs.
- WP2: research data generated in the survey and interviews (group and individual) were shared according to the principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" under an open access license through an open Knowledge Base in compliance with GDPR regulations.
- WP3: the analysis elements were shared as early as possible and validated through an open validation process with the community.
- WP4: the recommendations were shared as early as possible with an open license.
- WP5: the scientific publications presenting the analysis were published open access.

The Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results ensured that the relevant actions were compliant with the OS principles and the Horizon Europe requirements on Open Science. Regarding its communication activities, PALOMERA engaged and involved the identified stakeholders (as an example; RPOs, RFOs) in the co-design and co-creation of the project outputs, thus promoting open science practices and responsible research and innovation values through its open validation process.

⁵https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en (last accessed on 18 December 2024).

For the dissemination activities, the PALOMERA consortium members also produced two academic/research papers⁶ that are not yet published at the time of writing v2.0 of the DMP. These are:

- Dreyer M., Varachkina H., *Survey to the national libraries publication*
- Maryl M., Manista G., *Attitudes towards Open Monographs in the European Research Area*

Both papers were submitted to *LIBER Quarterly*, which is the peer reviewed, open access journal of LIBER, the Association of European Research Libraries, and are currently under review. *Liber Quarterly* is indexed in the Directory of Open Access Journals⁷ (DOAJ).

Authors will retain the intellectual property rights to comply with the open access obligations of Horizon Europe, persistent identifiers in the publications will be used (like DOI, ORCID for authors, and the Funder Registry for the EC as the funding agency), and the name of the action, the acronym, and the grant number amongst the metadata will be referenced.

Additionally, the project's outputs were made available in the PALOMERA Knowledge Base, which was built as a DSpace repository. Based on the stakeholders' needs, the collected documents in the Knowledge Base were analyzed and contextualized in the form of short articles published in the OAPEN Open Access Books Toolkit to map the state-of-the-art research on the OA book publishing landscape. Linking to further readings in the Knowledge Base encouraged findability and reuse. A data steward (OAPEN) monitored all data-related issues.

3.2 Findable

The data created during the project is findable mainly via Persistent identifiers in open repositories for reuse and adequately described in the metadata associated with these data. Also, to extend the findability beyond the persistent identifiers, the project's outputs are presented to the broader audience on the subpage of OPERAS website.

3.2.1 Hosting services, website, and data repositories

Project website

The PALOMERA subpage of the OPERAS⁸ contains an outline of the motivation for the project, the ways PALOMERA investigated the identified issues, and the target audiences for the recommendations and deliverables that arose from the work. All deliverables, poster presentations, webinar recordings are linked to the main sources; Zenodo, YouTube channels, Knowledge Base.

Practical information is also included, such as the timeframe for the project, a list of the members and partners within the consortia and links out to European Commission information, such as openly available grant details, programmes, and the amount of funding to be allocated across

⁶ Titles and authors should be considered provisional until the academic papers are finally released and published.

⁷ [Liber Quarterly: The Journal of European Research Libraries – DOAJ](#) (last accessed on 19 December 2024).

⁸ <https://operas-eu.org/projects/palomera/> (last accessed on 18 December 2024).

organizations. Once the project is concluded, the subpage will be moved to the “Past projects” section on the OPERAS website.

PALOMERA Zenodo community

Following established good practice in the management of Horizon projects, a dedicated Zenodo⁹ community was set up for the project. All PALOMERA deliverables are also added to the OPERAS Zenodo community. All deliverables, reports, datasets, presentation slides¹⁰ have been shared under CC-BY license. This enables assigning DOIs to the project outputs, ensuring their clear versioning and to link them to multiple Zenodo communities such as that of OPERAS. Furthermore, to ensure long-term archiving, all documents were uploaded in PDF/A format.

YouTube

Recorded public events organized by WP5 were uploaded through the Open Access Books Network (OABN) channel on YouTube¹¹. Participants were warned that the session was recorded, and their staying was a consent. The YouTube link to the recording was shared via OABN's dissemination channels (mailing list, Twitter, our website). All OABN videos are licensed CC BY, to enable sharing and reuse. This enhances the discoverability of the discussions and presentations that took place at our events and enables people to engage with them even if they couldn't attend a session in person.

Hosting environment of the Knowledge Base: a DSpace repository

The Knowledge Base of the PALOMERA project is hosted by OAPEN and set up as a DSpace repository. Beyond the project completion OAPEN continues maintaining the Knowledge Base at a technical level. The Knowledge Base is co-owned by the following beneficiaries: DARIAH, IBL PAN, OAPEN, UGOE, UNIBI, and the University of Coimbra. These institutions are entitled to use and exploit the jointly owned result. Thus, the owners will be working on the exploitation of the Knowledge Base in collaboration and discuss the potential ways the Knowledge Base can be kept updated after the end of the project.

The license used for the Knowledge Base is ODC Open Database License (ODbL)¹², which is a license intended to allow users to freely share, modify, and use this Database while maintaining this same freedom for others.

Integration of a selected set of project outputs to the Open Access Books Toolkit

To enhance the discoverability of resources developed in the project, a selection was highlighted and made available as part of the OAPEN Open Access Books Toolkit¹³. The Editorial Advisory Board of the OA Books Toolkit was involved in facilitating new content integration into the toolkit. A special task force of the Editorial Advisory Board worked together with PALOMERA authors on selecting content and transposing it into the toolkit. The toolkit articles functioned as an interface to the Knowledge Base collection of research providing overviews, contextualization and analyses

⁹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/palomera/?page=1&size=20> (last accessed on 18 December 2024).

¹⁰ A generic PALOMERA project slide deck can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14260638>

¹¹ <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCqayUVBBGe3XihI7wHtY1ZA> (last accessed on 18 December 2024).

¹² <https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/licence/odc-open-database-license-odbl> (last accessed on 18 December 2024).

¹³ <https://www.oabooks-toolkit.org/> (last accessed on 18 December 2024).

of the documents collected in the Knowledge Base. The articles in the OA Books Toolkit were grouped thematically and are easily accessible. Links for further readings redirect to the Knowledge Base hosted on DSpace. Keywords and facets are used to facilitate further browsing and searching the Knowledge Base.

3.2.2 PID Policy

PALOMERA Zenodo was a primary PID provider for project outputs. Besides, special care will be given to include PIDs from legacy metadata (e.g., if a policy document serving as raw data comes with one) to the project-level metadata schemas. Where possible, publications and underlying data sets were interlinked via their PIDs. The ORCID was used in project outputs (publications, deliverables, datasets etc.). All the data stored in Zenodo was backed-up on the DSpace repository under the same PID assigned.

3.2.3 Data and metadata standards

WP2, who was responsible for data collection, defined metadata associated with the data collection in the Data Collection Spreadsheet ([Appendix 1](#)) and Data Collection Methodology ([Appendix 3](#)). This includes structure and format of the contextual documents that provide descriptive metadata to the raw data. Dublin Core (DC)¹⁴ was used as a primary collecting schema.

The metadata used in the Knowledge Base was based on the DC standard and was set up as a DSpace repository with the following features:

- flexible metadata schema,
- easy content discovery and full text search,
- configurable submission forms and quality control workflows,
- responsive user interface,
- persistent handle.net urls,
- OAI-PMH server & client,
- indexing by search engines including Google Scholar,
- spreadsheet batch export and editing.

Zenodo's metadata is compliant with DataCite's Metadata Schema¹⁵ minimum and recommended terms, with a few additional enrichments. Export to other popular formats such as Dublin Core (DC) or MARCXML is applicable.

Zotero collection bibliographical metadata can be exported to the DSpace repository in various widely used bibliographic standards.

A selection of the research data and metadata collected in Zotero was imported into the Knowledge Base and mapped onto the Dublin Core metadata scheme of the DSpace repository. This ensures that rich metadata describes the digital objects in the Knowledge Base and that they are findable.

¹⁴ <http://dublincore.org/> (last accessed on 18 December 2024).

¹⁵ <https://schema.datacite.org/> (last accessed on 18 December 2024).

All documents made available in the Knowledge Base are publicly accessible and downloadable (individually or in bulk).

A dataset¹⁶ containing data from the Knowledge Base is also available on Zenodo in the PALOMERA community. This dataset contains:

- 633 policy documents, grey literature, research articles, reports, and outputs of other projects cover a wide range of OA policies for academic books, including funding mandates, institutional policies, and publisher guidelines in various formats (pdf, jpg, txt).
- Separate “excerpts” files (html, txt) with passages from those documents about OA policies to monographs.
- 36 anonymised interview transcripts providing insights into the perspectives of different stakeholders on OA policies for academic books.
- Metadata records in the Dublin Core schema (html), describing each resource. They contain elements like contributor (author, interviewer), date (accessioned, available, issued, snapshot), description (abstract, provenance), identifier (uri, handle), language, publisher, rights, title, type, subject (country, tag, stakeholder).

Contextual metadata for any code written to clean or analyse data was provided as inline annotation.

3.2.4 Data quality

Data quality was assured by:

- task performed by qualified and experienced members of the project,
- using approved procedures and templates specified in the Data Collection Methodology ([Appendix 3](#)),
- using international standards (for example ISO - 8601 for the time and date, ISO-3166-1 for the names of the countries, ISO - 15836 for Dublin Core Metadata),
- using the standardized method of pseudonymisation and file naming,
- using specialized software for automatic text translation (by DeepL service), text transcription (by Happyscribe service) and coding (by Computer Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis Software),
- manual correction of the accuracy of text translation and transcription done by the interviewer who is the native speaker of the language being translated,
- implementing other data cleaning procedures, in accordance with CURATED standards¹⁷, to confirm validity, completeness, consistency and uniformity including, as example: removing duplicates, fixing structural error, typos.

3.3 Accessible

PALOMERA makes a strong commitment to improve access to support material that enable data-driven policy improvement for Open Access books. The project released all created resources following internal Open Access and open data policies and implemented a licensing policy where CC-BY 4.0 for content and CC0 (for metadata) are the default options.

¹⁶ Maryl, M., Manista, G., Snijder, R., & Rosiński, C. (2024). PALOMERA Knowledge Base Dataset [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14513243>

¹⁷ <https://datacurationnetwork.org/outputs/workflows/>

However, because of the ethical reason it was not possible to share all resources collected or data generated within the project under an open license. Some data (e.g. raw interview recordings or interview transcripts) were not qualified to be openly accessible when interviewees did not consent to their publication.

For long-term preservation widely used, standard non-proprietary document formats (like PDF/A, MP3, XML) were used.

It is possible to harvest metadata records from the Knowledge Base (DSpace) through the OAI-PMH interface.

3.3.1 Access policy

Papers, documentation, and reports resulting from the project are published Open Access (CC-BY 4.0) and a copy of these documents is deposited in the Zenodo collection of the project. Each document created by the project was assigned a DOI. If need be, back-up copies can then be stored in the Knowledge Base.

Following the “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” principle, the consortium made the largest possible portion of such sensitive data sets available. As depicted in the chart below, in some cases, it remains to be restricted to the metadata level, while in other cases a summary of the data set or an anonymised version of it is available too. In other cases, the data was destroyed via a secured method described in Joint Controllers Rules and Procedures. The consortium followed a best reasonable effort principle to dedicate time and resources for data cleaning and anonymisation.

3.4 Interoperable

3.4.1 Formats interoperability

The project’s modus operandi was organised along open formats and rich contextual information which allowed easy access and maximal reuse potential for its outputs. As a token of interoperability, the PALOMERA project outputs are sustained by or indexed in other infrastructural components of the Open Access books landscape, such as the OAPEN Open Access Book Toolkit or the Open Access Books Network.

3.4.2 Vocabularies standards

Starting in M6, WP3 made the vocabulary and coding methodology used for the Computer Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis Software openly available after the work had been completed through the Zenodo community. All related information is available in Deliverable 1.3 Report on Analysis Findings¹⁸. In terms of vocabularies used for coding the qualitative materials, the

¹⁸ Laakso, M., Bandura-Morgan, L., Bazeliuk, N., Davidson, A., Dreyer, M., Iannace, D. E., Manista, G., Maciej, M., Matthias, L., Ozkan, O., Proudman, V., Păltineanu, S., da Silva Ferreira, N. H., Stone, G., Tummes, J.-P.,

project's own vocabulary (to be shared as open data) is shaped by the PESTLE¹⁹ analysis approach. The custom coding vocabulary can be exported and it is shared openly after completion of coding. The data is therefore available in PDF standard format.

3.5 Reusable

On the one hand, the project heavily relied on reusing already existing policy documents and bibliodata. During the data collection, special attention was dedicated to clearing reuse rights of such source material.

3.5.1 Documentation and licences

On the other hand, a clear licensing policy and commitments to rich documentation was necessary to enable the widest possible reuse of project outputs. To this end, where legally and ethically possible, the project applied CC-BY 4.0 license for its outputs by default, while metadata was made available under CC0 license. The content of the Knowledge Base, which was not produced by the project partners in the context of PALOMERA, is used according to the licences that were specifically chosen by their original authors. This licensing policy was implemented in a way that is easily readable both for humans and for machines.

A ReadMe file accompanies the data sets deposited in the repositories used for the project. The ReadMe file includes the methods of data collection, methods of managing missing data (where relevant), methods of data cleaning, variable names, abbreviations. It also includes details of the text of survey and interview templates, details of who collected the data and information regarding legal and ethical agreements relating to the data (e.g., consent forms, data licences), and details of the software used to generate or process the data.

4 Allocation of resources

4.1 DMP development timeline and responsibilities to update it

The PALOMERA project aimed to use this DMP as a project management tool to facilitate the development of a common understanding and shared data management solutions across the project participants. As such, all WPs of the project contributed to it via meetings with the WP leaders and written consultations carried out in an iterative fashion. OPERAS and OAPEN oversaw coordinating and leading regular updates of this DMP which evolved until M24. The DMP was internally updated at M17.

Wnuk, M., & Varachina, H. (2024). PALOMERA Deliverable 3.1 – Report on Analysis Findings. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14330282>

¹⁹ <https://pestleanalysis.com/pest-analysis/> (last accessed on 18 December 2024)

4.2 Resources allocated in project budget

The costs for making the data associated with the PALOMERA project FAIR were covered by the grant. A total of 3.5 PMs were allocated to task 1.3 Quality and Risk management plan to draft the data management. Another 2 PMs were allocated in WP3 to build the Knowledge Base where OAPEN Foundation served as Data Steward. During the project lifetime, DARIAH-EU guided the process that ultimately led to the deposit of relevant components of the project in data repositories.

OAPEN Foundation, scientific coordinator of the project served as a Data Steward in PALOMERA project with a main objective of the data sets and data records quality assurance. The budget allocated to setting up and maintaining the DSpace repository for the Knowledge Base was 7,108 EUR. In addition, 35,000 EUR were used for software development and redesigning the OA Books Toolkit, which served as the public interface of the Knowledge Base.

4.3 Sustainability plan for the project outputs

Sustainability of the project outputs is ensured primarily by OAPEN and OPERAS and involves Knowledge Base and Open Access Books Toolkit, project website and Zenodo content.

When the project ends it has been decided that the below organisations will be listed as the joint owners of the KB (in alphabetical order): DARIAH, IBL PAN, OAPEN, UGOE, UNIBI, and the University of Coimbra, with OAPEN playing the main technical and editorial role.

It is estimated that KB sustainability will incur the following costs:

- Maintenance and hosting of the DSpace repository: € 3,700 annual cost
- Effort: 0.1 FTE

After the end of the project, the PALOMERA web pages hosted on the OPERAS website will remain permanently accessible under the "Past Projects" section of the "Projects" menu. This approach ensures both long-term preservation and ongoing curation, as OPERAS manages all content on its website. It does not require any additional costs.

5 Data security

Work package task leaders were expected to have their back-up and storage policies in place followed by their own, local policies and back-up protocols using institutional cloud storage solutions (handled by their IT departments) and following the rules of GDPR. Google Shared Drive was used as a main platform for data storage. All partners of the project had access as a Content Manager or Manager. Access to the folder dedicated to personal data was restricted only to task leaders involved in personal data collection. After the project ends all data collected on OPERAS administered GoogleDrive will be accessible only by the administrator personnel engaged in the PALOMERA project for the period of at least 5 years after the end of project.

All details related to the data security are explained in section 6 'Ethical aspects'.

As described in the paragraph 3.2 Findable, project outputs were deposited and made openly available on the long term in trusted repositories like ZENODO and PALOMERA repository - Knowledge Base.

5.1 Storage and backup during the research process and after project ends

As a guideline for data backup and storage the 3-2-1 rule was applied. This is a reliable recovery method for ensuring that data is protected adequately, and back-up copies of the raw data are available when needed. The benefit of this approach is that some analysis can be performed on the data copies.

In terms of quantitative data collected during the project (e.g., survey) the original data was stored at the personal computers of the project partners of WP2 (UGOE) and the copy was transferred to the PALOMERA Google SharedDrive. The raw datasets of the survey responses and the questionnaire is now available in ZENODO²⁰, in Publikationen an der Universität Bielefeld²¹ as well as in the Knowledge Base.

All PALOMERA files were stored on Google Shared Drives, which has been available to all consortium partners since the start of the project. The Shared Drive is automatically backed up with built-in Google Drive settings. Only users with appropriate roles (e.g. Manager) can delete or restore files. Any loss i.e. accidental deletion can be recovered for up to 30 days. A manual back-up will be taken at the end of the project and stored in a separate location to ensure data availability upon request in the case where data loss has been identified after the 30 days. OPERAS takes the responsibility to ensure that the data will continue to be made available for at least a period of 5 years following project end.

The datasets with BPCs and bibliographic information were downloaded (or created as a result of a query) and together with the corresponding metadata uploaded to the Knowledge Base. The data acquired by the call to national libraries was ingested into the Knowledge Base, as well.

Qualitative data obtained from participants (video and audio recordings, notes from the meetings, etc) was stored at the personal computers of the project partners of WP2, WP4 and WP5, another copy was stored in a dedicated folder on Google Shared Drive and the third copy was maintained outside the workplace, on external drive, to prevent the possibility of data loss due to a workplace related error. Transfer data to the external drive was done in a timely manner, whenever new data or the new version of the data was available. After the project ends all the data from the personal computers of PALOMERA partners will be deleted. Also data saved on the software

Folders on Google SharedDrive dedicated to project's activities were structured by tasks, as follow:

- WP1 Coordination and Management
- WP2 Building the Knowledge Base
 - T2.1 Quantitative data collection
 - T2.2 Qualitative data collection
 - T2.3 Knowledge Base structure
 - T2.4 Data Collection methodology
- WP3 Analyzing the Knowledge Base

²⁰ Dreyer, M., Tummes, J.-P., & Graham, S. (2024). PALOMERA ERA Wide Survey Dataset [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13641415>

²¹ <https://pub.uni-bielefeld.de/record/2993125> (last accessed on 19 December 2024).

- o T3.1 Data coding, enrichment
- o T3.2 Conduct analysis
- o Prepared materials for analysis
- WP4 Recommendations and resources
 - o T4.1 Recommendations for institutional strategies and funder policies for OAB
 - o T4.2 Resources to support institutional strategies and funder policies for OAB
- WP5 Communication, dissemination, engagement
 - o T5.1 Communication strategy
 - o T5.2 Outreach and engagement
 - o T5.3 Management of validation
 - o T5.4 Maximising impact

For data that was subject of GDPR separate folders were created on Google Shared Drive with restricted access for the task leaders only.

6 Ethical aspects

All project partners agreed to apply the ethical standards and guidelines of Horizon Europe as specified in the updated Model grant Agreement, as well as professional and international standards and relevant national, EU and international legislation. With respect to personal data, all partners complied with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Project members are professionals with prior experience in survey study and interview related to the subject of open science. They have determined that this study does not require ethics approval by the Ethics Committee.

In the case of raw data and enriched data (including policy documents, survey data, interview data, data collected during the validation workshops and bibliodata), certain records contained sensitive data which prevented the consortium from openly sharing the full version of it.

During the informed consent procedure, the granularity approach was presented to the participants, with all levels of data sharing options and confidentiality.

Informed consent and information sheets were provided to the participants of interview sessions. Data sharing option (either pseudonymised or anonymised) was included in the informed consent.

All interview recordings by default were stored in the PALOMERA Zoom Cloud administered by OPERAS then transferred on the dedicated Google Drive folder with restricted access only to the Work Package Leaders and authorized members of WP2 directly involved in data collection. All interviews were transcribed and translated into English (if needed) by using HappyScribe and DeepL software, respectively. These softwares strictly adhere to the GDPR ensuring that data remains protected and compliant. According to the methodology protocol and materials provided to the participants, all the transcripts were pseudonymized for further analysis and when submitted to the Knowledge Base²².

²² <https://knowledgebase.oabooks-toolkit.org/search?query=interview> (last accessed on 18 December 2024).

Participants of Funder Forum meetings were introduced to the Privacy Policy²³ at the moment of the 1st invitation, although not legally binding, they accepted that meetings will be convened under the Chatham House Rule²⁴, which meant that participants were free to use the information received, but neither the identity nor the affiliation of the speaker(s), nor that of any other participant, may be revealed.

Data collected through two surveys that were distributed among Funder Forum participants were anonymized before publishing the results in the form of two articles and report²⁵. Mailing list of FF participants, as they agreed, will be used for further meetings of the Policy Forum that will be continued after the project ends.

Invited experts that have played a role as reviewers or presenters (speakers) taking part in validation activities, the OABN PALOMERA series event and panel session during the PALOMERA conference agreed that their personal data were publicly revealed, including video recordings published on Youtube channel²⁶ and pictures presented in the Validation report²⁷ and PALOMERA LinkedIn.

6.1 Safeguards for personal data handling

In practice, four concrete cases had been identified which involve personal data protection, three of which came from the context of project administration while one qualifies as research involving human participants.

These were:

- Personal data concerning the project partners managed by WP1,
- Personal data collected from attendees of public events (online or face to face, managed by the relevant partner in the WP1 and WP5),
- Interview and survey data managed by WP2, WP3, and WP4,
- Stakeholder database data managed by WP4 and WP5.

In principle, the data collection was not aiming at collecting sensitive data, however personal data was collected in certain cases. This data collection process strictly adhered to the GDPR regulation. The implementation of GDPR regulations was led by all beneficiaries and partners of the PALOMERA project bound by the Joint Controller Rules and Procedures established in April 2023. In this document there was a managed access procedure in place for authorized users of personal data.

The contact details of the Data Protection Officer (DPO) were available to all data subjects involved in the research led by that specific partner (qualifiable as data controller) through the informed consent and the information sheet Data Privacy Notice ([Appendix 5](#)). The Data Protection Officer was not notified of any personal data breaches. Technical measures were implemented to control systems such as devices, networks and hardware, which includes:

²³ <https://operas-eu.org/projects/palomera/privacy-policy-palomera/>

²⁴ <https://www.chathamhouse.org/about-us/chatham-house-rule> (last accessed on 18 December 2024).

²⁵ <https://zenodo.org/records/14330330> (last accessed on 18 December 2024).

²⁶ <https://youtu.be/rpZl8-oucPw?si=sU-r0T3PqVP9gEsy> (last accessed on 18 December 2024).

²⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/14265343> (last accessed on 18 December 2024).

- Firewall, anti-virus protection and updates of software that required to perform project's tasks,
- Data minimization,
- Pseudonymization and anonymization,
- Restricted access to the files and folders with personal data, protected by passwords changed in a timely manner.

All the partners involved in personal data processing included organizational measures in place, as such:

- Security policy,
- Other procedures that help the partner's organization to know what its obligations and steps are to be taken in a situation of a data breach,
- Due diligence to check the processor before their commitment if they are compliant with GDPR.

6.1.1 Informed consent

Informed consent forms were used as part of invitations to contribute to interviews conducted by partners engaged in WP2. All partners ensured that consent was obtained for all possible reuse scenarios and that the information sheet was compliant with the requirements of GDPR. Template of the informed consent is provided as [Appendix 2](#) to this DMP.

For public online events organised by OPERAS, OABN or other project partners, the PALOMERA privacy policy subpage (see footnote 23) created on the OPERAS website was linked in the Zoom sign up form (when it was organized as a webinar) or in the registration confirmation email (when it was organized as an interactive Zoom meeting). Informed consent for participation in all above-mentioned cases was sought at the time of the invitation. All data subjects could easily withdraw their consent and fully exercise their data access rights.

As a rule, PALOMERA only accepted participants for studies who were fully able to give informed consent. All participants were provided with an information sheet and, after being informed about the project, asked to sign a consent form. The consent form as well as the information sheet clearly stated the purpose of the project and the methodology used. It also described how the data is actually stored and who has access to it. All participants were pointed to their right to withdraw, and full contact details of a contact person were provided.

Five persons did not consent for publishing the transcript, even in an anonymous form. Their decision was fully respected. According to the informed consent statement, all personal data should be deleted from PALOMERA GoogleDrive, HappyScribe, DeepL and Zoom Cloud by December 31st, 2024.

Appendix 1 – Data Collection Spreadsheet

PROGRESS	6%	Useful resources	PALOMERA data collection methodology	PALOMERA Zotero tutorials folder
TASK	DESCRIPTION	DONE	OUTPUT	
Country:			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The focus should be maintained on policies regarding open access to academic books. Timespan: since 2012 (10 years), but in case there's no material in this timespan, or there are very pertinent documents older than that, we should include them. Keywords (to be used in local languages): [Country name] AND policy / recommendation / guidelines / study/ report/ AND open/ access /bibliodiversity / support AND monographs, books, publishing. For general context libraries and repositories should be queried for articles and grey literature regarding open access practices in particular countries. The identification of contextual documents should be informed by PESTLE categories. ROARMAP could be a good place to start your search for policies in a particular country. 	
Country Group:		General search tips		
Person responsible				
1. Local expert(s) consultation	Identify a local expert (or experts) on OA in this country (e.g. national OA coordinator, relevant ministry official, member of advocacy group) and consult the further steps, esp. whether there are national documents, which institutions are worth looking into and which reports/documents/survey should be considered. ROARMAP is also good resource for finding institutions and policies. Please list the experts name and capacity (e.g. Open Science Coordinator / Ministry official / RFO representative).	<input type="checkbox"/>	Expert(s) name and role/affiliation 1. 2. 3.	
2. Overall Notes	Document your research by adding notes about overall process and specificity of open access and book policies in this country, that could be useful later for the analysis (e.g.: what is difficult, what is missing or hard to find, stakeholder specificity, peculiarities in defining academic books).	<input type="checkbox"/>	Notes on challenges: Notes on country specificity: Ideas for analysis:	
3. National Policy Makers (regional where relevant)	3a. Identify which Ministries or government agendas are responsible for national policies regarding academic books. In strongly federalised countries look at governments on a regional level. Be as exhaustive as possible – we need to identify all relevant institutions in this group.	<input type="checkbox"/>	List of relevant National Policy Makers 1. Name in English [Name in the original language] 2. 3.	Comments
	3b. Collect relevant documentation looking for Open Access Policies on their websites or in search engines. You can also contact the institution directly asking for documents. Types. We are looking for the documents regarding the various activities with regards to OA to books: OA policies and recommendations, consultations, roundtables, programmes, outreach activities, special funding streams, strategic plans, laws, rules, green papers, white papers, roadmaps, declaration, role of OA in evaluation/research assessment mechanisms. Add the documents to the PALOMERA Zotero collection.	<input type="checkbox"/>	[Records added to the Zotero Library – don't paste them here, provide comments if necessary]	
4. Research Funding Organisations (RFO)	4a. Identify public and private institutions or programmes for funding research on a national level. Check local websites with guidelines on where to look for funding, or consult PALOMERA Funders list prepared by WP4. ROARMAP is a good resource too. Look at the websites of government agendas identified in the previous step as they may also have some funding streams and related policies. Be as exhaustive as possible – we need all relevant institutions in this group.	<input type="checkbox"/>	List of relevant Research Funding Organisations 1. 3.	Comments
	4b. Collect relevant documentation from identified institutions, looking for Open Access Policies on their websites or in search engines. If possible, check how the policies are implemented – are there websites or repository collections aggregating open access outputs that have been funded by the RFOs? Is the compliance checked (and how)? Describe it in the comments. Types. We are looking for documents regarding the various activities with regards to OA to books: OA policies and recommendations, specific grant requirements regarding publishing books, dedicated programmes and funding streams for OA books. You can also contact the institution directly asking for policies or documents. Add the documents to the PALOMERA Zotero collection.	<input type="checkbox"/>		
5. Research Performing organisations (RPO)	Identify Research Performing Organisations which may have Open Access Policy: Check three largest universities (by number of students, staff, or funding), academy of sciences (if applicable) and large research institutions. Please, ensure geographical diversity of the sample. The institutions should be located in different parts/regions of the country. Extend the search beyond the three largest RPOs when relevant (e.g. you have knowledge of smaller institutions adopting strong OA policies, eg. from ROARMAP). Use search engines to look for documents in national language: university/academy/institute + open access policy/mandate. If there's no policy, record it too. This is one of the key stakeholder groups and we need as many examples as possible.	<input type="checkbox"/>	List of RPOs with OA policy 1. Name in English [Name in the original language] 2. 3.	Comments
		<input type="checkbox"/>	List of RPOs without OA policy or strategy 1. Name in English [Name in the original language] 2. 3.	Comments (why the RPO has not have OA policy or strategy)
		<input type="checkbox"/>	[Records added to the Zotero Library – don't paste them here, provide comments if necessary]	
6. Publishers	Identify academic publishers and check whether they have any open access policies or programmes available focused on, or at least mentioning, books. Check the national publisher's association for any guidelines or policies. When looking for policies, note whether there is a) policy or programme, b) no policy or programme. Add documents to the PALOMERA Zotero collection.	<input type="checkbox"/>	List of Publishers with OA policy 1. Name in English [Name in the original language] 2. 3.	Comments
		<input type="checkbox"/>	List of Publishers without OA policy 1. Name in English [Name in the original language] 2. 3.	Comments
		<input type="checkbox"/>	[Records added to the Zotero Library – don't paste them here, provide comments if necessary]	
8. Libraries & Infrastructure providers	Identify infrastructure providers (repositories or digital libraries maintained by institutions or organisations) that may have policies, guidelines, or recommendations regarding OA to academic books. Identify key libraries and infrastructure providers and look for policies or recommendations. You can consult the local expert, OPERAS National Node or OpenAIRE NOAD, where applicable. In the case of Libraries, LIBER may help you with reaching out to key local entities. Add documents to the PALOMERA Zotero collection.	<input type="checkbox"/>	List of Libraries/RIs with OA policy 1. Name in English [Name in the original language] 2. 3.	Comments
		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	List of Libraries/RIs with OA policy 1. Name in English [Name in the original language] 2. 3.	Comments
		<input type="checkbox"/>	[Records added to the Zotero Library – don't paste them here, provide comments if necessary]	
9. General context	Collect contextual documents regarding open access to academic books in this country that have not been captured above. The identification of contextual documents should be informed by PESTLE categories, i.e. covering Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal and Environmental (PESTLE) aspects. Attention should be given to different aspects of the OA publishing, not only the legal framework. Document types: reports, articles, survey datasets on OA books and policies in particular country/region. Timespan: look for documents published since 2012 through search engines, scholarly databases and national repositories. You can use advanced search options to adjust the timespan or document's language. Keywords: When searching for documents use the following combination of keywords translated into local languages: [Country name] AND policy / recommendation / guidelines AND open/access / bibliodiversity/ support AND monographs, books, publishing. Add documents to the PALOMERA Zotero collection.	<input type="checkbox"/>	[Records added to the Zotero Library – don't paste them here, provide comments if necessary]	

Appendix 2 – Template informed consent

INFORMATION FOR PARTICIPATION IN PALOMERA INTERVIEWS

INTERVIEWER: (Enter interviewer name, surname, and organization)

USE OF YOUR PERSONAL DATA

We, as participants of the PALOMERA project, value your privacy and process your personal data in compliance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation.

Your **personal data** is any information related to you. **Processing** is any operation performed on the data.

According to the transparency principle, this document will provide you with information about the processing of your personal data as required by Articles 12, 13 and 14 of the General Data Protection Regulation.

ORGANIZATION NAME, partner in the H2020 Project PALOMERA, is acting as the data controller within the meaning of the General Data Protection Regulation. If you have any questions or concerns regarding the processing of your personal data, please contact NAME AND SURNAME (mail)

WHAT INFORMATION ABOUT YOU DO WE COLLECT AND PROCESS?

The following information about you are collected and processed within the Project:

- Name, surname
- E-mail address
- Affiliation / professional situation / occupation
- Audio and video recording of the interview

LEGAL BASIS FOR THE PROCESSING OF YOUR DATA

Your data is processed based on your consent (Article 6.1(a) of the General Data Protection Regulation) which you give by accepting this Notice.

FOR HOW LONG DO WE KEEP YOUR DATA?

Your personal data will be stored on a secured spreadsheet, stored on the G-Suite institutional drive of the PALOMERA coordinator [organization], until 31 December 2024. Your name will not be used in any project outputs or communication. Instead, a unique code will be applied when used in any publications and outputs from this project. During the project period, we will take all measures to keep your personal data safe and fully confidential.

USE OF DATA AND DISSEMINATION OF RESEARCH FINDINGS

The interviews will be transcribed and analyzed with support of Computer-Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis Software. Findings from the analysis will be published and made openly available.

The anonymized datasets, i.e. interview transcripts, will be made available for future research through a certified open data repository. Pseudonymisation means that your identity will be replaced with a pseudonym (a random ID generated by the research team). The deposited form of the data will be properly redacted to fully protect confidentiality, and available for reuse to the promotion of Open Science and FAIR Data Principles

BENEFITS OF PARTICIPATING

The direct benefits of participating in the research are that participants can share experiences and actively bring their knowledge; mostly, however, the benefits are indirect, they will be accrued by the SSH research community, as a whole, with a contribution to the development of scholarly information infrastructure.

FINANCIAL ASPECTS

There is no remuneration paid for participation.

SUPERVISION

The interviews are conducted by researchers at [enter the name of the organization] during the PALOMERA project. You can always contact the researcher overseeing the data collection with queries and comments regarding the interview (maciej.maryl (at) ibl.waw.pl).

The interviewer certifies that:

- The terms of the present consent form are made clear to the participant, and any question they may have will be answered before the interview.
- The interviewee is free to withdraw from the study at any time.

CONSENT FORM

I agree that I have read and understood the Data Privacy Notice²⁸ provided by [name of the organization.....].

Based on this explanation, I, [please provide your name and surname here] agree, by signing below, that the Joint Controllers may process my personal data as such: name and surname, e-mail address, including the data of special category like audio and video recording, in purpose to conduct the studies indicated in PALOMERA project Grant #101094270²⁹ and to contact me in the future regarding this project.

²⁸ <https://operas-eu.org/projects/palomera/privacy-policy-palomera/> (last accessed on 18 December 2024).

²⁹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101094270>, DOI: [10.3030/101094270](https://doi.org/10.3030/101094270)

PLEASE, CHOOSE THE APPLICABLE OPTION FOR THE DATA PUBLICATION

- I agree to the publication of the anonymized transcript of the interview, but I reserve the right to the final approval of the transcript. (In that case, the interviewer sends you the transcript and will publish it only with your approval or after introducing changes you demand).
- I agree to the publication of the anonymized transcript of the interview, and I waive the right to the final approval of the transcript. (In that case, the interviewer will not be bothering you with the transcript after the interview).
- I don't agree with the publication of the anonymized transcript of the interview.

DATE

PLACE

SIGNATURE

Appendix 3 – Data Collection Methodology

PALOMERA Data Collection Methodology

v.1.3. 24 February 2023

Authors & Contributors

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Advisory board validation: Mark Vanholsbeeck, Vincianne Gaillard, Emanuel Kulczycki

Reference documents

- [PALOMERA WP2 Workflow](#)
- [Workshop folder](#)
- [Visual guide](#)

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About this document: The purpose is to provide a detailed description of the research process sketched in the proposal. Based on an iterative process., first, on the kick-off workshop,

then on input from WP2 task leaders and WP3 leader, followed by inputs from the consortium and AB.

Scope

Subject

The project focuses on **policies regarding open access to academic books** by collecting documentation (policies and contextual material), surveying key stakeholders, and obtaining in-depth contextual knowledge through interviews.

Academic books are defined here as scholarly peer-reviewed books including monographs, book chapters, edited collections, critical editions, and other long-form scholarly works. When conducting research we maintain an inclusive approach, i.e. follow how the academic books are defined in each analysed country.

Geography

PALOMERA will address countries across the European Research Area through its activities, together with selected international cases for comparison. These countries will be involved either through study of existing policy documents and case-studies, or directly through interviews and surveys.

ERA countries are divided into 5-6 clusters for research purposes. Given the large number of ERA countries, we will attempt to make 5-6 clusters of ERA countries with a similar profile in terms of policies and challenges as a function of the analysis of the Knowledge Base, and where feasible formulate distinct recommendations for each of these clusters.

Country groups for data collection (not to be mistaken with clusters resulting from the analysis):

Group A IBL PAN: Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Ukraine, Moldova, Czechia, Slovakia

Group B DARIAH: Hungary, Romania, Bulgaria, Turkey

Group C Hanken: Finland, Sweden, Norway, Denmark, Iceland

Group D Coimbra: Portugal, Spain, Italy, Greece

Group E ZRC SAZU: Slovenia, Croatia, Serbia, Bos. Herz., Montenegro, N. Macedonia, Albania

Group F SPARC Europe (w/support of OAPEN & OpenEdition): Netherlands, Belgium, Luxembourg, France

Group G UGOE: Germany, Switzerland, Austria

Group H LIBER (supported by SPARC Europe): All libraries – asking for institutional strategies

Group I Jisc: UK, Ireland

Additional contextual material, including policies and other documents, will be collected for European Union and other countries and international entities beyond ERA, incl. Americas, Africa and Asia. Data collection will be guided by suggestions from consortium members and the project's Advisory Board.

Stakeholders

The analysis will take into consideration various actors involved in OA book publishing at various stages of the research lifecycle:

1. National science policy makers
2. Research funding organisations (RFO)
3. Research Performing organisations (RPO)
4. Publishers
5. Scholarly societies
6. Infrastructure providers
7. Libraries
8. Researchers

As will be described in more detail as part of the data collection strategy. The project will in particular focus on the policies and actions of the first three stakeholder categories.

Approach to analysis

To reflect the systemic complexity of OA book publishing, the collected materials will cover Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal and Environmental (PESTLE) aspects of the issue (as described in the Fig.1). We will focus on existing and planned policies to identify key challenges and factors contributing to both success and failure of their implementation. Failure of implementation, or absence of relevant policies will also be analysed in terms of possible systemic bottlenecks and obstacles.

Fig. 1. PESTLE framework in PALOMERA

Of central focus to the project is comparison of policies concerning academic OA books, with a targeted outcome of the project to create increased alignment of policies in the future. To achieve this the current policies will be systematically collected and reviewed in order to derive conclusions about the current state as well as potential constructive development paths forward.

Techniques

Desk research

Various materials on policies regarding OA to academic books will be collected and analysed: policy documents, grey literature, research articles, reports, and outputs of other projects (e.g. OPERAS-P interview transcripts and reports, OPERAS Business Models SIG survey, Knowledge Exchange reports). Special attention will be given to collecting quantitative datasets from various sources (incl. bibliographic and market data) which could be aggregated for new analytical insights.

A visual guide to desk research procedures (with embedded links) is available [in this file](#).

Fig. 2. Resources identification

Step one: Identification

1. **Assignment.** Consortium members are assigned to particular countries and responsible for identification of key stakeholders and documents.
 - 1.1. The assignment is done by the Country Group Leader in Cooperation with the WP2 leader. Where we lack expertise we may use a wider OPERAS consortium (esp. SIGs).
 - 1.2. Wherever possible, the identification and collection procedures should be consulted with local experts (e.g. national OA coordinators). The local specificity should be also taken into account (e.g. different ministries responsible for academic books).
 - 1.3. All assignments and progress are documented in the relevant country sheet of the [PALOMERA Data Collection Protocol](#).

Fig. 3. PALOMERA stakeholders

2. **Stakeholder identification.** Researchers responsible for a particular country start with identifying key stakeholders for each of the stakeholder groups (fig.2), using guidelines in table 1.
 - 2.1. The most important groups for the study are **national science policy makers, research funding organisations (RFOs) and research performing organisations (RPOs)**. In case of policy makers and RFOs we need an exhaustive list of all players in the country. As there are many more RPOs, we should focus on the largest institutions and other entities, suggested by experts or identified through search for policies.
 - 2.2. In the case of remaining stakeholders (Publishers, scholarly societies, libraries and infrastructure providers) we need to have a minimum 2 documents per category per country, unless there are no relevant policies (what also should be recorded).

- 2.3. Other types of stakeholders like researchers and projects will be targeted through a general search for contextual materials like articles and reports, described in greater detail below.
- 2.4. Identified stakeholders should be listed in the relevant slot of the [PALOMERA Data Collection Protocol](#) with the English name, e.g. Ministry of Science and Education; National Science Centre; Charles University in Prague. Please, ensure that the name is not ambiguous and will not be confused with other entities. Separate multiple names with semicolons (;).

Table 1. Stakeholder and document identification

Stakeholder type	Stakeholder identification	Types of documents (examples)
National science policy makers	Ministries or other government agendas responsible for national policies regarding academic books	OA policies and recommendations, consultations, programmes, outreach activities, special funding streams, strategic plans, laws, rules, green papers, white papers, roadmaps, declaration, evaluation mechanisms
Research Funding Organisations (RFO)	Public and private institutions or programmes for funding research on national level	Policies, recommendations, grant requirements concerning publishing outputs, special funding streams
Research Performing organisations (RPO)	Selected entities (universities, academies, research institutes) that have policies regarding academic books	Internal OA policies, internal research assessment policies
Publishers	Selected entities that have policies regarding academic books	Publisher's Policies regarding OA
Scholarly societies	Scholarly organisations	Recommendations, policies regarding OA
Libraries & Infrastructure providers	Institutions or consortia providing e-infrastructure for academic books	Relevant policies and recommendations.
General context	Other materials relevant for understanding the context of OA book policies in a given country	Reports, articles and survey datasets on OA books in particular country/region

3. Resource identification. For each of the stakeholders group the relevant resources should be identified (see Table 1 for guidelines). In case of policy makers, RFOs need an exhaustive list of entities in every country and make every possible effort to locate relevant documents produced by them. In other cases we work with selected resources that may be exemplary for a stakeholder group in a particular country (e.g. a University's OA policy, recommendations by a scholarly association). [PALOMERA Data Collection Protocol](#) provides a detailed, step-by-step description of the process.

3.1. The focus should be maintained on policies regarding open access to academic books.

3.2. **Timespan:** since 2012 (10 years), but in case there's no material in this timespan, or there are very pertinent documents older than that, we should include them). Rationale: a decade after the EC approach towards open science was codified ([EC 2012](#)) and implemented in Horizon 2020, which also had significant impact on national policies.

3.3. When searching for documents use the following combination of **keywords** translated into local languages: [Country name] AND policy / recommendation / guidelines / study/ report/ AND open/access AND monographs, books, publishing.

3.4. For **general context** Libraries and repositories should be queried for articles and grey literature regarding open access practices in particular countries.

3.5. The identification of **contextual documents** should be informed by PESTLE categories - attention should be given to different aspects of the OA publishing, not only the legal framework. However, the actual PESTLE classification will be applied to sources on the later stage (pre-coding level).

3.6. Once all the documents from the particular stakeholder are added to the Zotero library (see the next step), the researcher marks the stakeholder as done (tick the box).

3.7. In case book policies are missing or there are other difficulties with reaching stakeholders or identifying the expected content, a note should be made in the comments section.

3.8. Researchers are also welcome to note the challenges they encounter, as well as country specificity (e.g. in defining academic books) and thoughts for analysis. When in doubt, researchers should consult country group coordinators or WP2 leaders.

4. Adding resources to Zotero. All documents will be added to the [PALOMERA library on Zotero](#) (video tutorial for those steps as well as resources for basing training in Zotero will be provided).

4.1. Add the document record to the relevant country group folder in the PALOMERA library (you can also work on the record in your own zotero library and copy the final version to the collection).

4.2. Add the full text to the record if it was not added automatically

4.3. Check and enrich the metadata.

4.3.1. Use title for original language and short title for English version of the title (that could be abbreviated).

- 4.3.2. Check the following elements: title, short title, author(s), date, language, licence, URL, persistent identifiers.
- 4.3.3. Add relevant tags to the record - country code and stakeholder type

Fig. 4. Data collection and pre-processing

Step two: collection and pre-processing

5. **Selection.** From the documents identified in step one the research team will identify those which should be collected on the basis of two criteria:
 - 5.1. **Relevance.** Should the document, after a closer scrutiny, turn out to be irrelevant for the study (e.g. a policy does not mention open access, or refers solely to articles), the research team may wish to exclude it.
 - 5.2. **Saturation.** If there are too many documents (esp. contextual ones) for the given country, the research team may choose to resign from those which in high probability will not provide substantial new information in relation to other documents processed for this country.
6. **Contextualised abstract.** For each document to be collected, provide a contextualised abstract (300-500 words) containing the following information:
 - 6.1. Document's history (who issued the document, what was the purpose)
 - 6.2. The gist of the document (1-2 sentences-long summary of the main points)
 - 6.3. Open access policies to academic books (describe the relevance of the document to this topic)
 - 6.4. Add it to the document metadata field (abstract)
7. **Excerpts.**

- 7.1. From each document choose those passages that are relevant to the project. If the entire document is relevant we can collect the whole document. There is no limit to the length of a single excerpt but try to keep it as meaningful as possible and the parts not relevant to the scope of the project omit irrelevant parts to make later coding more time-efficient (e.g. if a policy is dedicated solely to OA books we need the entire document but if OA books are just mentioned in one paragraph of a larger document, the relevant bit should be extracted). When in doubt, consult a country group coordinator or WP2 leaders.
- 7.2. Machine-translate the passages into (UK) English, using deepl. Check if the translation makes sense for the reader.
- 7.3. For each excerpt add a separate note to the document record in zotero library with following elements:
 - 7.3.1. Title: Excerpt #1, Excerpt #2, ..., Excerpt #n,
 - 7.3.2. Optionally add a short description of the excerpt, please mark it clearly as Abstract and keep in parentheses. E.g.: [ABSTRACT: This excerpt discusses policies regarding scholarly editions.]
 - 7.3.3. Paste the excerpt in English, **use quotation marks in a clear way, so we know that the text comes from the documents**, for the text left out use [...].
 - 7.3.4. Tag the excerpt with relevant PESTLE tags
 - 7.3.5. Example of a note added to Zotero:

Excerpt #1

[ABSTRACT: This excerpt deals with infrastructures for open books.]

“The text of the policy excerpt [...] with unimportant parts omitted.”

Tags: Political, Technological

8. **Backup.** The library – both metadata and full texts - will be backed up by the IBL PAN team automatically through the Better BibTeX add-on and stored on the secured Google drive.

III. KNOWLEDGE BASE AND PRECODING

- Download – Zotero library will be downloaded as CSV (or other format) and stored securely on the project drive
- Knowledge base – part of the metadata and excerpts will be uploaded to the Knowledge Base and shared when possible.
- Pre-coding. The documents will be uploaded to the chosen CAQDAS programme (probably MaxQDA) and pre-coded for PESTLE elements

Fig. 5. Knowledge base and pre-coding

Step three: Knowledge Base & pre-coding

9. **Download.** Zotero library will be downloaded as CSV (or another format) with associated files and stored securely on the project drive.
10. **Knowledge base.** Part of the metadata and excerpts will be uploaded by T.2.3 to the Knowledge Base and made available publicly under fair use when not restricted by the licence. No personal data will be stored in the KB. The KB (the public database) will be a DSpace database that will reside on the servers of the IT company Atmire. It will be available to the public through the OAbooks toolkit - <https://www.oabooks-toolkit.org>
11. **Pre-coding.** The documents will be uploaded to the chosen CAQDAS programme (probably MaxQDA) and pre-coded for PESTLE elements. Pre-coding is the first iteration of the coding phase (the proper coding will be done by WP3) in which only PESTLE categories will be applied as codes to documents in order to facilitate further analysis. The output and experiences will feed into the second, analytical coding iteration in WP3. It will also inform the creation of the analytical coding scheme.

Bibliographic data collection

The bibliographic data collection will be provided by BASE. BASE collects bibliographic data from different sources like repositories (incl. DOAB), publishers (via Crossref), and other book related data providers (e.g. WikiBooks, Project Gutenberg, DNB Reihe O).

A data dump for book titles and book chapters is currently under preparation. The data structure will be the "base_dc format", which is an [extended DC format](#).

Another data collection will be provided by [OpenAPC](#), which provides oa book data with additional cost data.

Survey

[Note: this section will be elaborated after the preparation of the detailed survey methodology]

An ERA-wide survey on OA book publishing will be informed by desk research and widely disseminated among the key stakeholders in order to get important insights on policies, challenges, best practices and failures in implementation of OA book policies on various levels (institutional or national).

The survey should have two versions: RPOs & RFOs. It should be also considered to what extent the survey should target policy makers (or should it be done through interviews).

The aim would be to see not only how things are established on a national level (as described in collected documents) but also, how they actually work.

Interviews

[Note: this section will be further elaborated after the preparation of the detailed interview methodology]

A series of group and individual semi-structured interviews with selected stakeholders will allow for a more in-depth understanding of particular challenges and policies. Whenever possible, the interviews will be conducted in national languages to ensure wide participation of all actors. Each interview will be followed by a short case-study prepared by an interviewer to describe the national context of the discussion. All interviews will be transcribed and translated into English with the support of dedicated software.

Participants. Participants from stakeholder groups to be selected after the identification phase. E.g. We may use interviews when there's not enough documentation (e.g. no policies), but also where there is a policy and we want to learn about the formulation, implementation and evaluation processes.

GDPR. Data protection issues to be taken into consideration on the data collection phase, including consent forms and data storage issues, as well as possible anonymisation and publication of outputs.

Transcription. Each interview will be auto-transcribed (and corrected by the interviewer), machine-translated into English (and corrected by the interviewer).

Output. Interview output will contain:

- Metadata, depending on the consent: country, stakeholder, date, interviewee, PESTLE tags
- Contextualised abstract (description of the country context, links to relevant documents, explanation of the processes or events referred to in the interview)
- Interview text

Pre coding. Interviews will be uploaded to MaxQDA and pre-coded for PESTLE categories.

Knowledge base. To be discussed to what extent interviews will form a part of the Knowledge base (as full texts or selected excerpts)

Timeline

PALOMERA WP2 Workflow

[GANTT Chart for WP2 activities](#)

PHASE I (M1-M6) - Methodology setup and sources collection

PHASE II (M7-M10) - Survey and interview data collection

PHASE III (M11-M13)- Coding & Validation

PHASE IV (M14-M15) - Finalising, reporting, validation follow-up

PALOMERA ACTIVITIES			M	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15
		Month		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3
		Year		23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	24	24	24
Activity	Description	Tasks involved		PHASE I				PHASE II				PHASE III			PHASE IV			
	Milestones	ALL						MS2			MS3				MS4		MS6	
	Workshops & Events		WS1	WS2		WS3		WS4							E1			
A2.1	Hiring	ALL	█															
A2.2	Collection/selection methodology setup	ALL	█	█														
A2.3	Qualitative data records collection in Zotero	T2.2	█	█	█	█	█	█	█									
A2.4	Survey of quantitative datasets and survey results & records collection in Zotero	T2.1.	█	█	█	█	█	█	█									
A2.5	Knowledge base structure & coding scheme	ALL & WP3	█	█	█	█	█	█	█									
A2.6	Knowledge base prepared for data ingestion	T2.3																
A2.7	CAQDAS software bought	T2.2																
A2.8	Data collection & coding in the KB	ALL																
A2.9	Interviews methodology preparation	T2.2																
A2.10	Survey methodology preparation	T2.1																
A2.11	Survey and interviews conducted	T2.1&T2.2																
A2.12	Interview results & case-studies transcribed	T2.2																
A2.13	Knowledge base validation - preparation and	T2.3																
A2.14	Report preparation (D2.1)	ALL																

Activity #	Activity Description	Tasks involved	M Start	M End
A2.1	Hiring	ALL	-	M1
A2.2	Data collection methodology setup	ALL	M2	M2
A2.3	Qualitative data records identification in Zotero	T2.2	M2	M6
A2.4	Survey of quantitative datasets and survey results & records collection in Zotero	T2.1.	M2	M6
A2.5	Knowledge base structure & coding scheme	ALL & WP3	M1	M6
A2.6	Knowledge base prepared for data ingestion	T2.3	M2	M6?
A2.7	CAQDAS software selected and purchased	T2.2		M6
A2.8	Data collection & coding	ALL	M3?	M15
A2.9	Interviews methodology preparation	T2.2	M2	M5
A2.10	Survey methodology preparation	T2.1	M2	M5

A2.11	Survey and interviews conducted	T2.1&T2.2	M6	M9
A2.12	Interview results & case-studies transcribed and coded in the KB	T2.2	M6	M15
A2.13	Knowledge base validation - preparation and implementation	T2.3	M11	M13
A2.14	Report preparation (D2.1)	ALL	M13	M15

MILESTONES

MS2 - Knowledge base structure and the content coding scheme defined (M6)

MS3 - Survey and interviews conducted (M9)

MS5 - Knowledge base validated (M13)

MS6 - Pre-coded research data available for analysis in KB (M15) = D2.1

DELIVERABLES

D2.1 - Report on compiling the Knowledge Base (M15)

INTERNAL WORKSHOPS

WS2.1 - Identification of data, sources and collection [incl. stakeholders for interviews] (M1) - Kick off?

WS2.2 - Interview & Survey methodology (M2)

WS2.3 - KB structure & coding scheme (M3)

WS2.4 - Coding procedures (M6)

EVENTS

E2.1 - Validation workshop (during the consortium meeting or online?) M12/M13

Supporting documents

1. [ERA countries list with assignments](#)
2. [PALOMERA Data Collection Protocol](#) - Guidelines for data identification and collection in Zotero
3. Survey outline and questionnaire (to be prepared)
4. Interview scenario (to be prepared)

Appendix 4 – Interviewer Handbook

PALOMERA Interviewer Handbook

1. General aims

- 1.1. The interviews broaden our factual knowledge gathered from documents and surveys.
- 1.2. They concern WHO & WHY of the **OA policy creation and implementation**. In the absence of a policy, we are **equally interested WHY there's none and what are the factors behind it**. We aim to understand the processes behind the policies.
- 1.3. We ask our respondents in their professional capacities first and foremost about their immediate institutional experience as:
 - **policy makers** (national/regional policies),
 - **research funding organisations** (funders policies)
 - **research performing organisations** (institutional policies)
 - **publishers** (institutional policies)
 - **librarians** (institutional policies)
- 1.4. We need to specify, if they're speaking about their institution or general national/European context. As a rule, we prefer them speaking about their immediate sphere of experience.

2. Interview scenario

- 2.1. All interviews should be conducted with the use of the interview [scenario](#). For the group interviews we will use a [slightly different scenario](#), and will try to stick to more general questions (limiting the use of subquestions), so the interview is not too long.
- 2.2. We prefer the interviews to be conducted in English. However, we may also conduct them in other languages, but it means a bit more work with proofreading the translation ([check if happyscribe handles the automatic transcription in this language](#))
- 2.3. For interviews conducted in other languages than English, the interviewer needs to translate the questions **before** the interview.

3. Sampling

- 3.1. We aim at roughly 40 interviews, i.e. at least 35 individual interviews and 5 group interviews or focus groups (one per stakeholder group). Group interviews should cover up to 8 participants from different countries.
- 3.2. General sample aims:
 - Roughly 4–6 interviews per country group (depending on the group size).
 - Each ERA country covered (ambitious, just like us)
 - App. 8 interviews per each of 5 stakeholder categories, incl. one group interview per category.
 - Gender balance (+/- 10%)

- 3.3. WP2 leadership is responsible for the sampling and will instruct the country group leaders with regard to the expected demographic profile.
- Country group leaders propose a set of interviewees with demographic data (gender, country, stakeholder type) not later than 2 weeks before the planned interview.
 - WP2 leadership approves or asks for some changes regarding the overall sample (e.g. different stakeholder type or gender).
 - Once approved, WP2 leadership provides the country coordinator with a unique interviewee identifier (e.g. PAL01, PAL02, etc.) that should be used in handling the data.
 - If interviewee refuses, preferably find somebody else from the same country and the same stakeholder group.

4. Pre-Interview setup

- 4.1. Book the interview at least two weeks well in advance (in some cases it may take up to a couple of months, especially in the holiday period) using the [PALOMERA Interview Invitation Letter](#).
- 4.2. [Information for Participation and Consent form](#)
- This document is a template, please copy it and send it to the interviewee by filling in the yellow spaces (information about interviewer and interviewee) before.
 - Send a consent form to the interviewee and ask for a signed copy (scan) to be e-mailed back before the interview (answer their additional questions, if needed, but mind 4.4 below).
 - Pass the consent form to the WP2 leadership as soon as you receive it (before the interview).
- 4.3. Copy the link to the OPERAS Zoom meeting (Room 3, it is always the same link) and send it to the interviewee. You may also create a calendar event and invite the interviewee through this channel too.
- In order to avoid double bookings, it is essential to add meetings@operas-eu.org to all Google calendar invites. There will be a shared calendar where you can double-check if that zoom room is being use for that time slots. In addition, in order to be able to see which zoom room is being used, you must add which Zoom account is being used directly to the meeting name of the calendar invite: **[ZM#] PALOMERA WP# <Meeting Title>**
 - Zoom 3 – ROOM:
<https://us06web.zoom.us/j/8991816619?pwd=NzJtcUZyKytXNDcrOEZxMHpoRXBoQT09>
 - Calendar: subscribe to the meetings@operas-eu.org calendar to see all meetings.
 - Shareable link to Google calendar:
<https://calendar.google.com/calendar/u/2?cid=bWVldGluZ3NAb3BlcmFzLWV1Lm9yZw>
- 4.4. Make sure to send a reminder to your respondent approx. 48 h before the interview.

- 4.5. Do not send questions nor an interview beforehand unless they ask for them to avoid difficulties in conducting the interview. Otherwise, your interviewee would wait for certain questions to be asked instead of concentrating on what you expect. The description in the consent form will be enough.
- 4.6. Create your own [Interview scenario](#) (copy it from the document and then put to the [INDIVIDUAL SCENARIO](#) folder. Make sure that you put all the important information about the interviewee before the interview. You can adjust the scenario to the person, e.g. you can delete the questions which are only specified for some of the stakeholders group.

5. Technological setup

- 5.1. Be sure that you have a stable connection, quiet room and good microphone to facilitate the transcription.
- 5.2. Use a recording option on Zoom (Zoom to cloud recording is recommended as it keeps on recording despite the quality of your internet connection).
 - Make yourself the host of the meeting to record it.
 - Join the PALOMERA Zoom Room and find the option “make me a host” (it should be at the “user” toolbar, at the right corner). If asked, put the authorisation code —> **270379**
 - <https://us06web.zoom.us/j/8991816619?pwd=NzJtcUZyKytXNDcrOEZxMHpoRXBoQT09>
- 5.3. Use back-up audio recording, either through internal software on your computer (e.g. [Audacity](#)) or an external device like a voice recorder or a mobile phone, to preserve the interview in case of the Zoom failure.
- 5.4. Once the interview is finalized, the recording will be stored in the OPERAS cloud. Please, email Yannick (Yannick.Legre@operas-eu.org), who administers the Zoom account, that you conducted the interview and ask him to move the recording to the [Google Shared Drive \(GDPR restricted\)](#). In case of technical problems with the outputs, consult WP2 leadership.

6. Beginning of the interview

- 6.1. Remind interviewee that we're recording (as stated in the consent form).
- 6.2. Inform that we have scheduled one hour, and you'll do your best to finish on time. It is important that the interviewee knows that you are working towards keeping the time constraints, so they can cooperate.

7. Interview as a conversation

- 7.1. The goal is not to ask all the questions, but to get all the answers.
- 7.2. Repeating back what you heard when you're not 100% sure in a more complex argument can help - and makes them feel listened to. At the beginning, its also a good way to connect with the interviewee
- 7.3. Your main task is to show your interviewee that you listen and this knowledge/experience is very important for you.
- 7.4. When you ask a new question, relate it to the previous ones (e.g. *you already mentioned X, now tell me about Y*). You can also announce the start of a different topic (some prompts are already in the scenario).

- 7.5. You can slightly modify questions, if you feel that a certain part was answered and other aspects not.
- 7.6. Furthermore, you don't have to ask questions or sub-questions if what we need was already spelled out earlier. Move to the next questions, instead of having the interviewees repeating themselves.
- 7.7. Follow-up questions are intended to be used if the interviewee's answers are short, and you need additional prompts to make them talk.

8. Clarity

- 8.1. Ensure that all statements are self-evident and will be understood by transcript readers. If they refer to the shared knowledge between you and them, ask them to elaborate it (e.g. if the interviewee refers to the project both of you know, it would be good to ask for the explanation for the sake of the transcript and further analysis).
- 8.2. If you're not sure if you understood something correctly, wait until they finish and ask a follow-up question (e.g. *you said X, does it mean that Y, or...*). Don't be afraid to do this, they are usually happy to elaborate.

9. Timing

- 9.1. For individual interviews we expect roughly 5 minutes per section, except for political aspects which should take about 10 minutes. In sum, that makes 45 minutes, so there's still room for slight elaborations within the hour you have. Please use this as a guide only – there may be interviewees with specialised knowledge on one of the sections and then the balance will be different.
- 9.2. For group interviews we may expect slightly longer discussion, and we'll work with the limit of 90 minutes. We don't expect everyone in the group to respond to each question, but rather to highlight general provisions. Try to facilitate in such a way that the quieter participants also contribute.
- 9.3. All throughout the conversation control time and progress in the questionnaire.
 - You never know which question will take longer with this particular interviewee, so it's hard to time all the questions. But if we know that somebody's an expert in a particular field, make sure that they answered the set of questions relevant to their expertise.
 - Before the interview you can add specific times to the sections to remember, when you definitely need to move on.
 - Don't be afraid of short answers and quick interviews, as long as they remain on topic. (The longer the interview, the longer the transcript).
 - Throughout the interview use a dedicated copy or a printout of the questionnaire and cross out the questions asked or those that don't need to be asked because you already have answers (or know that the interviewee will not be able to answer).
- 9.4. The final section is optional. We should have time to ask whether there's something else worth mentioning, but we don't need it if timing doesn't permit.

10. Managing interviewees

- 10.1. Interviewees are willing to cooperate and to deliver the goods, so they will respond to your confident management of the interview.

- 10.2. If an interviewee gets off-topic or ventures into a digression you may say: *that's very interesting, so please keep it in mind, and we'll get back to it later on.* (And they are willing to cooperate and wait). Take a note and return to this issue in the last section.
- 10.3. If someone talks a bit too much about a topic and this conversation is not bringing anything new, you can cut it off politely using the argument of respecting their time (*I promised to take 60 minutes of your time and really wouldn't want to bother you longer...*).

11. Group interview

Although all the information provided so far applies also to the group interviews, there are some additional issues to be discussed.

- 11.1. In the group interview we aim at getting the information about all the countries but also we want to have a group dynamics and comparison. So, you don't have to ask all the questions to all participants but rather have the first one responding in detail and then ask the rest if it looks similar in their countries or if they want to add something. Not everybody needs to respond.
- 11.2. Use the general questions and the follow up only to get the discussion going. There's a chance that they'll cover everything without prompting.

12. Transcription and translation

- 12.1. Tool: [happyscribe](#) (GDPR-compliant)
- 12.2. Interviewers request individual accounts from Gabriela (subaccounts to WP leader account) on happyscribe, where they may transcribe the content of interviews. Only interviewers see/listen to the interviews.
- 12.3. Once the transcription is finalized it will be stored by the interviewer in the dedicated folder for interview materials in the file named with PAL_ID.
- 12.4. If the interview was conducted in a non-English language, the interviewer uses DeepL to translate the interview into English and proofread it.
- 12.5. Once the translation is finalized it will be stored by interviewer in the dedicated folder in the file named with PALOMERA_ID and _en
- 12.6. The following conventions should be followed:
 - We use standard transcript procedures, i.e. transcribing what was said, without pause marks (like "yyyy....", "mmmm", etc.) or timestamps.
 - Questions and comments by the interviewer should be clearly marked by "INTERVIEWER" and **bold font**.

13. Publication

13.1. Consent for publication

- Interviewees will decide in the consent form whether they will later consider the publication of the interviews as open research data.
 - They should specify in the consent form whether they would expect the interview to be anonymised beforehand (i.e. removing all references to actual entities).
- 13.2. The transcribed interview (anonymised) will be sent to the interviewee for the authorisation.

13.3. The accepted version will be published in the Knowledge Base.

14. After the interview

14.1. Please, provide some notes right after the interview. There should be 3-5 most important points from the interview. It can be regarding the specificity of the country OA books landscape or other reflections concerning interview scenario (e.g. if the question was not clear for the interviewee etc.), or interviewee's capacity (e.g. lack of knowledge in certain areas that could be important for us).

14.2. Notes should be written on top of the Individual scenario file (document).

Appendix 5 – Data Privacy Notice

Data Privacy Notice – PALOMERA project

In accordance with art. 13 para 1 and art. 26 of the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (hereinafter referred to as: “GDPR”) we would like to inform you that your personal data is processed in the proper manner and in accordance with GDPR provisions and provisions of statute on personal data protection, and:

1. The Joint Controllers of your personal data are the following beneficiaries and partners of the PALOMERA project:

a) Name: OPERAS AISBL

Contact: Quai aux Briques 76, 1000 BRUXELLES, Belgium

b) Name: STICHTING OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHING IN EUROPEAN NETWORKS (OAPEN)

Contact: Prins Willem-Alexanderhof 5, DEN HAAG, 2595 BE, Netherlands

c) Name: SVENSKA HANDELSHÖGSKOLAN (HANKEN)

Contact: Arkadiankatu 22 Helsinki, 00100 Finland

d) Name: INSTYTUT BADAŃ LITERACKICH POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK (IBL-PAN)

Contact: ul. Nowy Świat 72, Warszawa, 00-330, Poland

e) Name: STICHTING LIBER (LIBER)

Contact: Pr Willem Alexanderhof 5, DEN HAAG, 2595 BE, Netherlands

f) Name: UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA (UC)

Contact: Paço das Escolas, COIMBRA 3004-531, Portugal

g) Name: DIGITAL RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE FOR THE ARTS AND HUMANITIES (DARIAH ERIC)

Contact: 54 boulevard Raspail, 75006, Paris

h) Name: ZNANSTVENORAZISKOVALNI CENTER SLOVENSKE AKADEMIJE ZNANOSTI IN UMETNOSTI (ZRC SAZU)

Contact: Novi Trg 2, Ljubljana, 1000, Slovenia

i) Name: GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITÄT GÖTTINGEN STIFTUNG ÖFFENTLICHEN RECHTS (UGOE)

Contact: Wilhelmsplatz 1, Göttingen, 37073, Germany

j) Name: STICHTING SPARC EUROPE (SPARC Europe)

Contact: Watermanstraat 98, Apeldoorn, 7324 AK, Netherlands

k) Name: Jisc LBG

Contact: 4 Portwall Lane, Bristol, BS1 6NB, United Kingdom

l) Name: OPEN BOOK PUBLISHERS COMMUNITY INTEREST COMPANY (OBP)

Contact: 40 Devonshire Road, Cambridge CB1 2BL, United Kingdom

2. The Joint Controllers of your personal data have appointed a person supervising the correctness of personal data processing, who can be contacted via the email address: maciej.maryl@ibl.waw.pl.

3. Your personal data will be processed for the following purpose:

a) to carry out research activities described in EU funded PALOMERA project reference to the Grant #101094270 – based on Art. 6 para 1 letter “a” and “f” of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

4. The recipients of your personal data will be:

a) beneficiaries of PALOMERA project involved in data collection and analysis (which are

listed in point 1), including only persons employed and authorized by them to process data as part of their official duties and,

b) your personal data (after pseudonymization) may be disclosed to the data processors that provide Controllers with services, support with ICT systems and provide with and operate the IT systems and softwares used for the proper performance of the Joint Controllers' tasks and,

c) if necessary, your personal data may also be disclosed to entities authorized to receive your data based on applicable legal provisions.

5. The Joint Controllers may entrust the processing of personal data to the processors while fulfilling the requirements resulting from the GDPR, in particular art. 28 of GDPR.

6. The data will not be made available to external entities, to a third country or international organization.

7. Your personal data will be stored for the period necessary to achieve the purposes set out in point 3, but no longer than 31 December 2024.

8. You have the right to access your data and are subject to the law: the right to rectify, delete, limit processing, the right to transfer data, the right to object, the right to withdraw consent at any time.

9. You also have the right to withdraw consent at any time without affecting the lawfulness of the processing that was carried out based on consent before its withdrawal. Withdrawal of consent to the processing of personal data may be directed to INSTYTUT BADAŃ LITERACKICH POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK (IBL-PAN):

by e-mail: maciej.maryl@ibl.waw.pl;

by post (with the note "Data protection PALOMERA") to the following address: ul. Nowy Świat 72, Warszawa, 00-330, Poland

10. You have the right to lodge a complaint to the President of the Office of Personal Data Protection if you feel that the one of the Joint Controllers processing your personal data violates the regulations on the protection of such data.

11. Your data will not be processed in an automated manner and will not be profiled.

